

IMPROVING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOOD-PLASTICS COMPOSITES BY PARTICLE SURFACE TREATMENT IN SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

In this work, wood-plastics composites (WPC) were prepared based on linear medium density polyethylene (LMDPE) and maple wood flour. In particular, a simple dry-blending technique was used to initially blend the components which had similar sizes. This step was followed by compression molding to produce rectangular plates for analysis. Furthermore, wood surface treatment with maleated polyethylene (MAPE) in solution was performed to improve the adhesion between the matrix and the reinforcing particles. Also, the effect of wood content was studied by using different concentrations (0, 10, 20 and 30% wt.). From the samples produced, a complete characterization in terms of morphology (scanning electron microscopy), mechanics (tensile, torsion, and flexural properties), as well as density and hardness was done. From the tensile stress-strain curves, modulus, strength, and strain at break are reported, while only shear and flexural moduli were studied for torsion and bending tests. The results show that the simple dry-blending technique can be effectively used to produce homogeneous composites; i.e. good wood flour dispersion in the matrix. Also, successful surface treatment of the wood led to improved mechanical properties. The results showed that it was possible to substantially improve the moduli of the neat matrix (by up to 132%) for the range of conditions tested.

INTRODUCTION

For several years now, wood-plastics composites (WPC) were developed because of their low costs and high specific properties (per unit weight) compared to composites based on glass fibers or other inorganic reinforcements. Nevertheless, WPC main drawback is low compatibility between the reinforcement and most polymer resins; i.e. polyolefin like polyethylene and polypropylene. This limitation also applies for natural fibres (lignocellulosic) like hemp, flax, jute, sisal, and so on. For this reason, methods to improve adhesion between both phases were developed and a review was published by Faruk et al. [1].

From an engineering point of view, optimization of processing technologies and cost reduction are two general aspect that need to be taken into account when producing a new part. This is why investigations on equipment and processes were made, in parallel with improvement of the raw materials. In our group, a focus was made on using powder metallurgy processing and to adapt these techniques for polymers [2]. Since all the materials can be obtained in a powder form, it is proposed to use these particles and perform dry-blending instead of standard melt-blending in a twin-screw extruder as generally done for most thermoplastic resins. This methodology is believed to be highly cost effective, while limiting thermo-mechanical and oxidative degradation of both materials: matrix and reinforcement. This processing methodology has already been successfully applied for injection molding [3], rotational molding [4-5] and compression molding [6].

In our previous work [6], the simple dry-blending method was able to produce good WPC based on ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) and wood particles up to 30% wt. The samples were produced by compression molding and the results showed that good dispersion and good contact

between each phase was achieved. From the samples produced, the moduli (tension, flexion and torsion) increased by up to 97%, but important loss in tensile strength (from 41.6 to 8.4 MPa) and elongation at break (from 859 to 17%) was the result of poor adhesion between wood particles (polar and hydrophilic) and the polyethylene matrix (non-polar and hydrophobic).

So the objective of this study is to determine if a pre-treatment of the wood surface can be done to improve the mechanical strength of WPC. In this case, maple wood flour is used to reinforce linear medium density polyethylene (LMDPE) for wood concentrations up to 30% wt. The surface treatment applied is a combination of mercerization (NaOH) and maleated polyethylene (MAPE) grafting in solution. The composites are produced by compression molding and characterized in terms of morphology, density, hardness, as well as tensile, torsion, and flexural properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

The matrix used was Hival 103508 LMDPE (Ashland, Canada). This polymer is in a powder form with a particle size distribution mostly between 80 and 400 microns. Its density is 938 kg/m³ with a melting temperature of 128°C. For reinforcement, maple wood flour (PWI Industries, Canada) was mechanically sieved between 125 and 250 microns to get particles within the same range of LMDPE. Using similar sizes for both types of particle is believed to improve dry-blending homogeneity, while limiting material segregation when handled [7]. For wood surface treatment, sodium hydroxide (NaOH, ACS grade, EMD chemicals, Canada), maleated polyethylene (MAPE, Epolene C26, Westlake Chemicals, USA) and 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (TCB, HPLC grade, J.T. Baker, USA) were used as received.

Wood Surface Treatment

The same procedure as reported elsewhere was performed and consists of two steps [8]. In the first step, standard mercerization was applied. The wood particles were placed for 30 min in 2% NaOH at 60°C with high intensity mixing. The material was then washed 6 times with distilled water and dried overnight in an oven at 60°C. This step is mainly performed to clean the surface of the wood particles (remove waxes, resins and impurities) and expose (better access) the hydroxyl groups. In the second step, the mercerized wood particles from the first step were placed in a 1% MAPE solution in TCB at 90°C for 30 min under high intensity mixing. After filtration, the treated wood was dried overnight at 60°C in an oven. For each step, the wood content in solution was limited to 10% wt. to get good contact between the phases, while limiting mixing problems.

Sample Production

The samples were produced by dry-blending of the wood particles and LMDPE powder. This was performed via high shear mixing in a Black & Decker model Cyclone at 18,000 rpm for 2 min. Then, the samples were produced in a steel mold having dimensions of 120x120x3.0 mm³. Compression molding was performed on a Carver (C series) laboratory press at 170°C. The material was pre-heated for 3 min, then 2 tons of force was applied for 8 min and cooling was done for 8 min via circulating water. To study the effect of wood content, four concentrations were used: 0, 10, 20 and 30% wt. The samples were then cut directly into the molded plates to perform all the characterization. More details can be found in our previous works [6, 8]. Before use, wood particles were dried overnight in an oven (80°C) to remove any residual moisture/volatiles.

Density

Density measurements were performed with a gas (nitrogen) pycnometer model Ultrapyc 1200e (Quantachrome Instruments, USA). The reported values are the average of at least three measurements with standard deviation.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) were taken to characterize the morphology of the composites. First, the samples were broken in liquid nitrogen. Then, the exposed surfaces were coated

with Au/Pd and images at different magnifications were taken using a JEOL JSM-840A SEM operated at 15 kV.

Tensile Properties

Tensile tests were performed on a mechanical tester model 5565 (Instron, USA) with a 500 N load cell. Type V dog bone sample according to ASTM D638 were tested at room temperature with a rate of 10 mm/min. For each material, five specimens were used to get an average and standard deviation.

Flexural Properties

Three point bending tests were made on a model 5565 (Instron, USA) universal mechanical tester with a 50 N load cell. Rectangular bars with dimensions of 80x12x3 mm³ were used. The tests were performed at room temperature and 10 mm/min with a span of 60 mm. Five samples were tested for each material to get an average and standard deviation.

Torsion Properties

Shear tests were performed using the torsion rectangular geometry on an ARES rheometer (TA Instruments, USA) at room temperature. Rectangular bars with dimensions of 80x12x3 mm³ were characterized. First, strain sweeps were made to determine the limits of the linear viscoelastic range of each material. Then, frequency sweeps between 0.05 and 200 rad/s were performed at a deformation of 0.05%. Three samples were used to get an average and standard deviation.

Hardness

For hardness, each sample was measured by the Shore D scale (model 307L durometer). The values reported are the average of ten measurements with standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wood Surface Treatment

In our previous work [8], it has been shown that the surface treatment of the wood particles was successful under the conditions described in the Experimental section. Using thermogravimetry (TGA), Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), it was clear that MAPE was grafted on the wood particles. In Figure 1, clear differences between untreated and treated wood can be observed; the latter has a more uniform texture (white spots), which can be associated to the presence of MAPE. So the objective is to determine the effect of this surface treatment on the properties of the resulting composites. This is presented next.

Figure 1: Typical SEM images of the wood particles: untreated (left) and treated (right).

Composite Morphology

SEM images were taken at different magnifications to get two main information: composite homogeneity (uniform distribution of wood particles in the matrix) and interfacial state (contact/adhesion between both phases). Typical images are presented in Figure 2 for treated and untreated wood.

Figure 2: Typical SEM images of the composites (10% wt.) made from untreated (left) and treated (right) wood particles at different magnifications.

From Figure 2, images at low magnifications (25X) show that homogeneous samples were produced without void or defects. Nevertheless, the texture is again very different between treated and untreated wood which is an indication that different interactions are present between both phases. This can be clearly seen at higher magnifications (1,000X). There is clear gaps between the untreated wood particles and LMDPE, which is not the case for treated wood. This morphological difference is again an indication that the surface treatment was effective and should have an effect on the mechanical properties as discussed next.

Density

Density results for the composites are presented in Table 1. It is clear that untreated samples have lower density, probably due to the presence of voids at the wood-polymer interface as presented in Figure 2. Overall, density increases with wood content since the density of wood is higher than LMDPE. In our case the untreated wood had a density of $1543 \pm 36 \text{ kg/m}^3$, which increased to $1714 \pm$

51 kg/m³ after the treatment. This density increase can be associated to partial filling of wood porosity with grafted MAPE.

Wood (% wt.)	<i>Untreated</i>	<i>Treated</i>
0	946 ± 6	
10	991 ± 18	1004 ± 24
20	1021 ± 7	1040 ± 22
30	1121 ± 29	1048 ± 9

Table 1: Density (kg/m³) of the composites based on treated and untreated wood.

Tensile Properties

Tables 2-3 present the tensile properties of the samples produced. It is clear that increasing wood content substantially improved the tensile modulus (E) of the untreated wood samples by up to 75% at 30% wt. wood over the neat polymer matrix. Nevertheless, due to poor adhesion between untreated wood particles and LMDPE, tensile strength (σ_y) decreased from 17 to 12 MPa at 30% wood content. Also, elongation at break (ϵ_b) decreased (from 2188 to 42%) as expected due to low elasticity of wood fibres (more brittle material).

On the other hand, surface treatment of wood particles led to higher tensile modulus. For example, at 30% wood, a 10% increase in Young modulus was produced when compared to the untreated sample (from 372 to 410 MPa). More importantly, tensile strength increased with wood content for treated particles (from 17 to 21 MPa) unlike untreated ones. This again is a clear indication of good interaction between the reinforcement and matrix [9]. As a down side, better interfacial stress transfer led to more brittle materials as lower elongations at break were obtained: only 31% for the treated wood compared to 42% for untreated one at 30% wood content.

Wood (% wt.)	E (MPa)	σ_y (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)
0	212 ± 10	17 ± 1	2188 ± 101
10	282 ± 13	15 ± 2	87 ± 9
20	328 ± 35	14 ± 1	51 ± 11
30	372 ± 22	12 ± 1	42 ± 4

Table 2: Tensile properties of the composites based on untreated wood.

Wood (% wt.)	E (MPa)	σ_y (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)
10	304 ± 17	18 ± 1	72 ± 11
20	355 ± 16	19 ± 1	43 ± 4
30	410 ± 46	21 ± 1	31 ± 6

Table 3: Tensile properties of the composites based on treated wood.

Bending Properties

For the flexural modulus, a clear increase with wood content is also observed in Table 4. For the untreated particles, adding 30% wood increases the value from 872 to 1502 MPa (72%). But an even more important increase was obtained when treated wood was used. In this case, the modulus increased from 1502 to 1738 MPa (16%) compared to untreated wood, which represents a 99% increase over neat LMDPE.

Wood (% wt.)	<i>Untreated</i>	<i>Treated</i>
0	872 ± 36	
10	1006 ± 71	1253 ± 64
20	1256 ± 103	1562 ± 146
30	1502 ± 79	1738 ± 150

Table 4: Flexural modulus (MPa) of the composites based on treated and untreated wood.

Shear Properties

From the raw data of the rheometer, the complex modulus as a function of frequency was obtained to compare the samples. As it is usually the case, the curves at different wood contents are parallel to each other, thus enabling a single frequency analysis to be performed [10]. So the data reported in Table 5 are the complex shear moduli (G^*) for a frequency of 1 rad/s. Again for torsion results, wood addition clearly increases shear modulus. For untreated wood particles at 30%, the shear modulus increased from 349 to 812 MPa (132%). But curiously in this case, there is no significant difference between treated and untreated wood within experimental uncertainty. This results indicates that wood content is more important than surface adhesion for shear modulus and must be related to the way the stresses are applied on the samples compared to tensile (pure tension) and flexural (combination of tension and compression with some shear) tests.

Wood (% wt.)	<i>Untreated</i>	<i>Treated</i>
0	349 ± 16	
10	542 ± 54	502 ± 26
20	624 ± 51	640 ± 87
30	812 ± 17	829 ± 57

Table 5: Shear modulus (MPa) of the composites based on treated and untreated wood.

Hardness

Table 6 present the hardness results for the composites. Once again, hardness increases with wood content as reported elsewhere [6]. Also, the effect of surface treatment is again negligible within experimental uncertainty.

Wood (% wt.)	Untreated	Treated
0	59 ± 1	
10	58 ± 1	61 ± 2
20	59 ± 2	63 ± 2
30	65 ± 2	66 ± 1

Table 6: Hardness (Shore D) of the composites based on treated and untreated wood.

Discussion

From the work performed, it is clear that simple dry-blending of the raw materials is an efficient methodology to produce polymer composites for two reasons. First, the process is less costly as no extruder or other melt processing equipment is needed. This uses less energy and imposes less thermo-mechanical, as well as oxidative, degradation on the components. Processing is also much faster since less steps are involved. Second, dry-blending enables to work with high viscosity materials since blending is performed in the solid state. This is why homogeneous materials can be produced if careful selection of the particle sizes is made and optimum conditions are used to mix all the components.

The SEM presented clearly showed that homogeneous samples can be produced (uniform wood distribution) with good mechanical properties as obtained in the first parts on this study [6, 8]. Also, wood particle surface treatment produced much higher mechanical properties: up to 132% increase in modulus. This opens the door to several possibilities in the future to develop processes based on powder technology for polymer composites using other matrices and reinforcements. There is also the possibility to increase the number of components to produce more complex structures. One possibility is the addition of a chemical blowing agent (powder form) to produce composite foams [5]. Developments into this direction are currently being done.

CONCLUSION

In this work, wood-plastics composites (WPC) were produced using LMDPE as the matrix and maple wood flour as reinforcement. In particular, the simple dry-blending technique was used to blend both components in the solid state using a high shear mixer. From these powder blends, composite plates were produced via compression molding. Also, a pre-treatment of the wood particles was applied (NaOH/MAPE) in solution. Finally, the effect of wood content between 0 and 30% wt. was studied. Based on the results obtained, several conclusions can be made:

For the wood particle sizes used (80-250 microns), homogenous samples were produced without voids or defects using the simple dry-blending technique combined with compression molding.

The wood surface treatment was effective as changes in parts morphology (broken surface texture) and density were observed. This was also confirmed by tensile strength results as the values decreased with increasing untreated wood content (from 17 to 12 MPa), while an increasing trend was observed for treated wood (from 17 to 21 MPa).

Adding up to 30% wt. of untreated wood can increase the tensile (75%), torsion (72%) and flexural (132%) moduli of neat UHMWPE. Nevertheless, higher improvement (especially in tension and flexion) were obtained when treated wood was used.

Finally, these results are encouraging but more work is needed to further improve the properties of WPC and to apply this methodology to other polymers and particles, especially for the production of multicomponent systems.

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